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Cybercrime: Current Trend and Steps to be Taken in the Present Context of Nepal

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Introduction

A crime is an action or omission which constitutes an offence and is punishable by law. A crime is an offence against a public law. Criminal law is the laws of a state or country dealing with criminal offenses and their punishments. Criminal law concerns the system of legal rules that define what conduct is classified as a crime and how the government may prosecute individuals that commit crimes. Investigating, apprehending (arrest), charging, and trying suspected offenders are regulated by the law of criminal procedure. The paradigm case of a crime lies in the proof, beyond reasonable doubt, that a person is guilty of two things. First, the accused must commit an act which is deemed by society to be criminal, or *actus reus* (guilty act). Second, the accused must have the requisite malicious intent to do a criminal act, or *mens rea* (guilty mind). Modern criminal law has been affected considerably by the social sciences, especially with respect to sentencing, legal research, legislation, and rehabilitation. Among several crime, Cybercrime is also an increasing one. This may not constitute guilt act and guilty mind though it is crime as state classified it such as just crossing photos of anyone on social media after which state takes it as crime. The world is progressive towards society 5.0 and Nepal is not an exception evidenced from e-governance to virtual agriculture [1&2]. Smart village to online vehicle maintenance, digital sign language, and online product tracing are found at project level in Nepal [3, 4, 5, 6&7] whose dark side may be more digital action, some space of cybercrime.

According to Handler and Jaishankar "Cyber Crime is a crime committed against a person or group that intentionally harms the physical, mental or emotional well-being of the individual or group by using Internet and mobile." In General Cybercrime refers to criminal activities that are carried out using computers, networks, or other digital technologies. It involves the use of technology to commit various illegal activities or to target individuals, organizations, or governments. Cybercriminals

typically exploit vulnerabilities in computer systems and networks to gain unauthorized access, steal sensitive information, disrupt or damage computer systems, commit fraud, or engage in other illicit activities.

Brief History

The very first incident in the history of cybercrime was registered in the year 1820. In a French textile factory, owner Joseph Sherp Meri Jake worldly built an automatic machine to weave clothes, and the workers there tried to destroy the structure of the industry because of losing their jobs. Which was considered the world's first Cybercrime.

- 1. Technically:** 1960s and 1970s: The first instances of cybercrime emerged as early as the 1960s and 1970s. Hackers, known as "phone phreaks," manipulated the telephone network to make free long-distance calls. The famous hacker Kevin Mitnick began his hacking activities during this period.
- 2. 1980s:** With the rise of personal computers, cybercrime started taking new forms. Computer viruses, like the Morris Worm in 1988, exposed the potential dangers of malicious software. Hackers began breaking into computer systems for personal gain, curiosity, or political reasons.
- 2.. 1990s:** The proliferation of the internet and the growth of e-commerce led to an increase in cybercrime. Online fraud, credit card theft, and identity theft became prevalent. Hackers organized into groups, and high-profile attacks occurred.
- 4. Early 2000s:** Cybercrime became more sophisticated with the emergence of botnets and large-scale attacks, such as distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks. Worms like Mydoom and Sobig caused significant disruption.
- 5. Mid-2000s to Present:** Cybercrime gained more attention from law enforcement and

governments. Financial institutions became targets, resulting in online banking fraud and theft of sensitive financial information. Ransomware, which encrypts files and demands a ransom, became a major threat.

Types of Cybercrime Include:

1. **Hacking:** Unauthorized access to computer systems or networks to gain control over them, steal information, or disrupt their operations
2. **Phishing:** Sending fraudulent emails, messages, or websites that appear legitimate to trick individuals into revealing sensitive information, such as passwords or financial details.
3. **Identity Theft:** Stealing someone's personal information, such as social security numbers, credit card details, or bank account information, to commit fraud or other criminal activities
4. **Malware Attacks:** Distributing malicious software (malware) that can infect computers or networks, allowing cybercriminals to gain control, steal information, or cause damage. Denial of Service (DoS) and Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS)
5. **Attacks:** Overloading a computer system, network, or website with excessive traffic to render it inaccessible or unusable.
6. **Ransom Ware:** Encrypting a victim's data and demanding a ransom payment in exchange for restoring access to the data.
7. **Cyber Stalking and Harassment:** Using digital technologies to stalk or harass individuals, often through social media, email, or instant messaging.
8. **Online Fraud:** Various fraudulent activities conducted online, such as online scams, pyramid schemes, or fake online auctions.
9. **Cyber Espionage:** Unauthorized access or theft of classified or sensitive information from governments, organizations, or individuals for political, economic, or military advantage.
10. **Cyber Terrorism:** Using technology to carry out acts of terrorism, such as hacking into critical infrastructure systems or spreading propaganda online.

Current Scenario of Cyber Crime: Nepal

In recent times, cybercrime has become a headache all over the world. According to Telegraph out of

every 10 people one person is a victim from cybercrime while everyone's second 14 people are pray of the cybercrime. According to a report published by the United Nations, one in three women who have access to the Internet in the world are victims of cyber violence in some way. According to a study conducted in 86 different countries, female online users between the ages of 18 and 24 have faced sexual harassment and bullying online.

According to the 2022 Global Cyber Security Index published by the International Telecommunication Union, the international regulatory body of the telecommunications sector 94 ranking out of 160 countries shows that Nepal cyber security is at risk from security point of view. In developed countries, there are many crimes related to bank account and credit card Fraud. In Nepal, using other people's names and pictures on social networks, defaming them through e-mails and other social networks, threatening them and asking for money in various types of nude pictures, putting a potter couple on the Internet. There are many cases of hacking the websites of government and other organizations and publishing and distributing obscene and sexual content on the Internet through computers or other means that spread distortions in the society. Recently, the news of Nepal police arresting a Chinese citizen while foreign Chinese hackers were withdrawing money from the duplicate card shows that bank and credit card related crimes are increasing. As cybercrimes become money mandate, their next attack is on banks and financial institutions but it has been found that only a few banks in Nepal have invested in information Security, while the fact that cybercrime is mostly from social networks in Nepal has been seen from various studies. Even global Scenario of Cyber Crime demonstrates somehow similar [13,14].

Major Reasons for Increasing Cybercrime in Nepal

1. **Increasing Internet Penetration:** Nepal has witnessed significant growth in internet penetration in recent years. As more people gain access to the internet and digital technologies, it creates a larger pool of potential targets for cybercriminals.
2. **Lack of Awareness and Education:** Many individuals and organizations in Nepal may not have adequate knowledge or awareness about the risks and preventive measures associated with cyber security. This lack of awareness makes them more vulnerable to cybercrime.

3. **Weak Cybersecurity Infrastructure:** Nepal, like many developing countries, may face challenges in establishing robust cyber security infrastructure and systems. Insufficient investment in cyber security measures, lack of cyber security professionals, and outdated technologies can create vulnerabilities that cybercriminals can exploit.
4. **Limited Legal Framework:** The absence of inadequacy of comprehensive cyber security laws and regulations can hinder effective prosecution and deterrence of cybercriminals. The legal framework needs to keep pace with the evolving nature of cyber threats.
5. **Economic Factors:** Socioeconomic factors such as unemployment, poverty, and limited opportunities can push some individuals towards engaging in cybercriminal activities as a means to make money.

The way forward for Problem Solving: Nepal

To control cybercrime in Nepal, several measures can be taken at various levels. Here are some key steps that can be considered:

1. **Strengthening Legal Framework:** Enhance and enforce existing cyber security laws and regulations in Nepal. Develop comprehensive legislation that addresses various forms of cybercrime and includes provisions for investigation, prosecution, and punishment of offenders.
2. **Establishing Cyber security Policies:** Develop and implement national cyber security policies, strategies, and frameworks to guide cyber security efforts across different sectors. This includes defining roles and responsibilities of relevant government agencies, private organizations, and individuals in combating cybercrime.
3. **Enhancing Law Enforcement Capabilities:** Invest in training and equipping law enforcement agencies with the necessary skills and tools to investigate and respond to cybercrime incidents effectively. Develop specialized cybercrime units or task forces dedicated to tackling cyber threats.
4. **Promoting Public Awareness and Education:** Conduct awareness campaigns to educate individuals, businesses, and organizations

about the risks and preventive measures related to cyber security. This includes promoting safe online practices, educating about common cyber threats, and encouraging reporting of cybercrime incidents.

5. **Building Cyber Security Workforce:** Invest in developing a skilled cyber security workforce through education, training, and certification programs. Encourage the growth of cyber security professionals, both in the public and private sectors, to address the increasing demand for cyber security expertise.
6. **Collaboration and Information Sharing:** Foster collaboration and information sharing among government agencies, private organizations, and international partners. Establish platforms for sharing threat intelligence, best practices, and experiences to stay updated on emerging cyber threats and strengthen collective defenses.
7. **Enhancing Public-Private Partnerships:** Foster collaboration between government entities and private organizations to jointly address cyber security challenges. Encourage public-private partnerships in areas such as information sharing, research and development, and capacity building.
8. **Implementing Cyber Security Controls:** Encourage organizations and individuals to implement robust cyber security measures, including firewalls, antivirus software, encryption, strong passwords, and regular software updates. Emphasize the importance of secure practices in areas such as online banking, e-commerce, and social media.
9. **International Cooperation:** Collaborate with international organizations and neighboring countries to address transnational cybercrime. Establish mechanisms for cooperation, information exchange, and joint investigation of cybercrime cases that cross borders.
10. **Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation:** Regularly assess the effectiveness of cyber security measures and adapt strategies based on emerging threats and evolving technologies. Monitor and evaluate the implementation of cyber security policies and initiatives to ensure their efficiency and effectiveness.

Implementing these measures requires a coordinated effort from government agencies, private sector entities, educational institutions, and individuals. By combining legal, technical, educational, and collaborative approaches, Nepal can make significant progress in controlling cybercrime and protecting its digital landscape.

Cyber Crime is a serious challenge brought by science and technology. Its control is further challenged by the involvement of organized criminal groups. Cybercrime is not limited to a specific geographical area, which has led to the realization of the need for international treaty agreements. Joint organizations such as the United Nations have also raised the issue of Cyber Security with priority, but Nepal should force in this direction. Since the efforts of one nation alone cannot achieve success in controlling cybercrime, cooperation and commitment among nations seems imperative and soul essential.

References

1. A.K. Mishra, Nepal Ananda, P. S. Aithal, (August 2022). Industry 4.0 Concept for Nepal - Operating Virtual Farming Industry. PP- 31-35, Proceedings on Future Trends in ICCT and its Applications in IT, Management and Education, Editors: Dr. Krishna Prasad, K., Dr. P. S. Aithal, & Dr. A. Jayanthiladevi, ISBN: 978-81-949961-8-7, DOI: <https://zenodo.org/record/7215189>
2. Bhagat, C., Mishra, A. K., & Aithal, P. S., (2022). Model for Implementation of e-Government Services in Developing Countries like Nepal. International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT, and Education (IJCSBE), 6(2), 320-333. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7139657>.
3. Rajat Pokharel, Mishra, A. K., & Aithal, P. S., (2021). Practicability Assessment of Smart Village Project: A Case of Sandakpur Rural Municipality, Ilam Nepal. International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS), 6(2), 265-281. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5799392>.
4. Jha, P. B., Mishra, A. K., & Aithal, P. S., (2023). Operation of Vehicle Maintenance System in Context of Developing Countries Emphasizing Nepal. International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT, and Education (IJCSBE), 7(1), 267-279. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7790868>.
5. Pandey, A., Dhakal, A., Khadka, P., Bhandari, B., Jha, P. B., Mishra, A. K., & Aithal, P.S., (2023). Emergence of Sign Language Recognition System into Text. International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML), 7(2), 91-101. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7915843>
6. Mishra, A. K., Jha, P. B., & Aithal, P. S., (2023). Business Operation Using Identification of Product in Context of Developing Countries Emphasizing Nepal. International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML), 7(1), 112-126. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7798162>
7. Goswami, A. (2018). Impact of Cyber Security in different Application of E-Governance. Journal of Advances and Scholarly Researches in Allied Education, 15(4), 65-70. doi: [10.29070/15/57309](https://doi.org/10.29070/15/57309)
8. Articles published by the United Nations International, Telecommunication Union European union, Asia pacific telecommunication community.
9. Bulletins published by Nepal Telecommunication Authority
10. A Study on Cyber Crime Cases in Nepal: Challenges and Recommendations 2022, National Judicial Academy Nepal
11. A study report published by the Internet Client Complaint Center.
12. FBI internet Crime Report Federal Bureau of Investigation.
13. Information Security Forum. (2018). Threat Horizon 2020. Information Security Forum. Retrieved from https://www.securityforum.org/uploads/2018/03/ISF_Threat-Horizon-2020_Executive-Summary.pdf
14. Kumar, D., & Panchanatham, N. (2015). A case study on Cyber Security in E-Governance. International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology. Retrieved from <https://www.irjet.net/archives/V2/i8/IRJET-V2I846.pdf>

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